

Problem-Based Learning: Systematization of evidence on its efficiency
Aprendizagem Baseada em Problemas: Sistematização de evidências sobre sua eficiência

Douglas Oliveira Pedrozo¹ Regiane Máximo Siqueira²
Simone Borges Simão Monteiro³

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ABSTRACT

The application of problem-based learning methodology can contribute significantly to educational practice, thus acting as complementing traditional teaching models. The article aimed to analyse the methods of assessment of problem-based learning in the context of higher education and to propose an assessment model. A systematic review of the literature was conducted, based on the Consolidated Meta-Analytic Approach Theory, with searches carried out in the Web of Science and Scopus indexed databases. In total, 22 articles were selected, whose results showed that the most commonly used assessment methods to verify the effectiveness of problem-based learning include pre- and post-tests (gain tests), interviews, Likert scale questionnaires, and multiple-choice tests. The recommendation to use pre- and post-tests stands out, as they allow for the formation of more homogeneous experimental groups and lend greater robustness to the analysis of the methodology's efficiency.

Keywords: Active methodology. Gain tests. Improvement of teaching. PBL.

RESUMO

A aplicação da metodologia de aprendizagem baseada em problemas pode contribuir significativamente para a prática educacional, atuando como um complemento aos modelos tradicionais de ensino. O objetivo deste artigo é analisar os métodos de avaliação da aprendizagem com base em problemas no contexto do ensino superior e propor um modelo de avaliação. Foi realizada uma revisão sistemática da literatura, baseada na Teoria da Abordagem Meta-Analítica Consolidada, com buscas realizadas nas bases de dados indexadas Web of Science e Scopus. Foram selecionados 22 artigos, cujos resultados mostram que os métodos de avaliação mais comumente utilizados para verificar a eficácia da aprendizagem com base em problemas incluem pré- e pós-testes (testes de ganho), entrevistas, questionários com escala Likert e testes de múltipla escolha. Destaca-se a recomendação de utilização de pré- e pós-testes, por permitirem a formação de grupos experimentais mais homogêneos e conferirem maior robustez à análise da eficácia da metodologia.

Palavras-chave: Metodologia ativa. Testes de desempenho. Aprimoramento do ensino. PBL.

¹ Mestre em Administração e Negócios pela Universidade Federal de Itajubá, Doutorando em Engenharia de Produção pela Universidade do Estado de São Paulo, UNESP, São Paulo, São Paulo – Brasil. douglas.pedrozo@unesp.br

² Doutora em Engenharia de Produção pela UFSCar. Professor Adjunto de Engenharia de Produção da UNESP. Universidade de São Paulo, UNESP. São Paulo, São Paulo – Brasil. regiane.maximo@unesp.br

³ Doutora em Engenharia de Produção pela Universidade Federal de São Carlos (UFSCar). Professora do Departamento de Engenharia de Produção da Universidade de Brasília. Brasília, Distrito Federal – Brasil. simoneborges@unb.br

1. Introduction

The teaching and learning process in different spheres generally uses traditional practices and methodologies based on memorisation or repeatedly solving exercises, without stimulating logical reasoning and creating an environment for investigation, making teaching uninspiring and tiring for students (Zulyusri et al., 2022).

There is, indeed, a need to train people to think critically and reflect on reality. The challenge is to create methodologies that can improve the student learning process and spark students' interest and motivation to study the different subjects offered in both basic education and higher education courses. In this sense, problem-based learning (PBL) and project-based learning (PBL) are teaching methodologies that involve students more actively in learning to solve a problem or carry out a project (Bayram & Deveci, 2022).

The PBL methodology consists of presenting a problem to students, who are then guided to solve it. Its application can promote student autonomy in the learning process (Zulyusri et al., 2022). Furthermore, according to Kasuga et al. (2022), PBL stimulates critical and creative thinking, allowing students to understand concepts more deeply while focusing on problem solving and project development.

Lawless et al. (2018) pointed out that PBL has been used for decades and involves the use of interdisciplinary contexts, such as social studies, as a context for engaging in real-world problem solving, deepening students' understanding and providing flexibility in the application and transfer of knowledge/skills.

However, problem-based learning encompasses many cognitive challenges. Students are challenged to understand a problematic situation, as well as clarifying the causes of the problem, deciding on important facts to investigate, and generating hypotheses for a solution (Song et al., 2006). In addition, it requires students to apply reasoning, questioning, research, and critical thinking to find a solution to the problem. Therefore, there is a need for monitoring by people who are prepared and trained to guide students in the best way possible in order to obtain concrete results (Ferraz Filho et al., 2017).

According to Rahman et al. (2023), measuring the effect of applying this methodology can be influenced by several factors, such as educational level, living environment, learning outcomes, and sample size. According to the authors, the problem-based learning model is fundamental for developing students' potential, preparing them to face the 21st-century job market, which requires increasingly qualified professionals.

This article aims to examine methods for assessing problem-based learning in higher

education and, based on this, suggest an assessment model. To achieve this objective, a systematic review of the literature was conducted, according to the Consolidated Meta-Analytic Approach Theory, with searches carried out in the Web of Science and Scopus indexed databases.

2. Methodology

This is a systematic literature review (SLR), using the Consolidated Meta-Analytic Approach Theory (TEMAC in Portuguese – *Teoria do Enfoque Meta-analítico Consolidado*) methodology. The integrative approach adopted allows researchers to identify the main points of different studies and to synthesise these results in a clear and objective manner, which summarize the knowledge and gather what has already been discovered on the topic of interest (Mariano & Rocha, 2017).

The search was conducted in the Web of Science and Scopus databases. The keywords used in the search were: “effectiveness*” OR “self*assessment*” AND “project-based* learning*” OR “problem-based* learning*” OR “pbl* method*” OR “N-gain”. A publication year limit of 2020-2024 was applied. The search was conducted in September 2024.

The following inclusion criteria were adopted as follows: articles in English that addressed the areas of exact and social sciences: Science Technology, Engineering, Computer Science, Public Administration, and Business Economics, which addressed some method of evaluating the efficiency of PBL. Therefore, articles in other languages, or those that did not present a methodology for evaluating PBL, were excluded. Furthermore, as this study focuses on higher education, articles highlighting the application of PBL in primary education were not considered. Initially, 209 articles were selected for evaluation and analysis.

Co-citation and bibliographic coupling analyses were performed using the VOSviewer programme. Co-citation and bibliographic coupling play a fundamental role in representing the structure of knowledge in a specific area, as well as in establishing connections between different studies and authors. The study was guided by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist (Moher et al., 2009), resulting in 17 articles of interest (Figure 1).

By applying the reverse snowball method described by Wohlin (2014), five additional manuscripts were included in the sample, totalling 22 articles addressed in this study. Reverse snowballing refers to the use of the reference list to identify new articles to be included (Wohlin, 2014). This process was carried out in order to cover as many articles as possible on the topic of interest in this review, so that the integrative model could be developed later.

Figure 1: PRISMA representation of the search performed

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Co-citation

In the co-citation map extracted from the WOS and Scopus databases, only articles with a minimum of two citations were considered. Five clusters were recorded in WOS: blue (20 items), red (18 items), green (14 items), yellow (13 items) and lilac (11 items) (Figure 2). Each node represents an author and is labelled with the author's name and year of publication. The size of each node indicates the influence or frequency of citations, while the colours and connecting lines represent clusters or relationships between authors.

Figure 2: Co-citation map – WoS

Each colour represents a thematic area that is most frequently co-cited. The blue cluster contains articles related to the application of the PBL methodology in sustainability topics related to education. It could be noted that the most prominent author is Guerra et al. The red cluster consists of articles related to the application of the PBL methodology in the field of medical education and prominent authors such as Barrows et al. and Noordegraaf-eelens et al.

The authors in the green cluster present articles with themes focused on the application of educational research using the PBL method of learning assessment. The leading authors in this theme are Savery et al. and Hattie et al. The purple cluster addresses the evaluation of technologies applied in education and virtual reality, with Anderson et al. being the most prominent author. The yellow cluster also refers to the medical field and the use of interactive teaching tools, with Yew et al. as the main author.

Four clusters were found in Scopus as follows: red (7 items), green (5 items), blue (3 items), and yellow (2 items) (Figure 3). In Scopus' co-citation analysis, it could be observed that the red cluster include authors such as Syahril et al., Fortuna et al. and Ramadã et al., and these studies address learning in the field of engineering. These authors emphasise the need for continuous learning and the optimisation of learning in engineering, each one addressing different but complementary aspects. Syahril et al. focused on innovation in pedagogy and the adaptation of curricula to meet the demands of the ever-evolving industrial labour market. Ramadã et al. complemented this topic with psychosocial and motivational factors in engineering learning. Fortuna et al. could explore the connection between theory and practical application through the use of advanced laboratories, simulations, or partnerships with industry.

Figure 3: Co-citation map – Scopus

The green cluster includes authors such as Prasetya et al. and Febrianti et al. The studies in this cluster address the use of technologies in learning and entrepreneurship. The blue cluster highlights the book by Christensen, which reports on how students' psychological issues can affect learning. Finally, the yellow cluster includes authors Guo et al. and Ahmad et al., who

reported on the use of PBL methodology for learning in higher or vocational education.

3.2. Bibliographic Coupling

The bibliographic coupling analysis was performed to identify the connection between documents based on the bibliographic references they share. This technique is useful for identifying the common theoretical basis among recent studies and understanding how research is interconnected. The bibliographic coupling map revealed a variety of distinct clusters, each one representing a specific area of research.

The analysis shows a network of authors, likely based on co-citation or co-authorship relationships. The WOS bibliographic coupling generated five different clusters (Figure 4).

In the green cluster, authors Obi et al. and Moradi et al. could share the application of PBL, focused mainly on the development of practical and applicable skills for engineering students. Both authors investigated the efficiency of PBL in developing fundamental skills in higher education environments, such as problem-solving, teamwork, and critical thinking, which are considered essential for professionals in the field.

The red cluster comprises the main authors Sukacke et al. and Bertel et al., therefore acting as main nodes. These studies focused on the use of PBL methodologies to promote active and engaged learning. Sukacke et al. analysed the PBL efficiency in improving students' skills based on active learning environments. Bertel et al. could explore the impact of PBL on promoting critical skills and student engagement.

Figure 4: WOS Bibliographic Coupling

The blue cluster includes authors such as Contreras-Espinosa et al. and Bukumiric et al. They are relatively independent, with few direct connections to other central groups. These

authors explore the use of PBL to promote interpersonal skills, especially communication and teamwork in higher education. The purple cluster comprises authors Morselli et al. and Zamir et al. The authors use PBL to develop cross-cutting competencies and interpersonal skills, especially motivational ones. The yellow cluster includes authors Fan et al., Soubra et al. and Ota et al. They discuss how the PBL pedagogical approach strengthens the development of essential skills, such as critical thinking, problem solving and communication, especially in the fields of medicine and education.

The Scopus bibliographic coupling generated 11 different clusters (Figure 5). Thus, only clusters with more than five items are addressed, and these clusters are denoted as red, blue, green, and purple. Based on some visible characteristics, the blue cluster included the authors Chen et al. and Zarouk et al. It is noteworthy that this is the most influential group, given the size of the connections and the node. The presence of extensive connections indicates that this group has a high frequency of co-citations or collaborations, suggesting a central and widely cited research topic. Chen is the most influential author in this group, probably indicating that this author and his publications are at the centre of discussions in this area of research. Chen et al. and Zarouk et al. analysed the benefits and challenges of implementing PBL, especially in engineering education. Both studies highlighted that PBL could promote practical and transferable skills, such as problem solving and collaboration.

Figure 5: Scopus Bibliographic Coupling

The green cluster includes authors such as Amin et al., Liao et al. and Saqr et al. The

connections in this cluster suggest a line of research that is parallel or complementary to that of the blue group, but with a slightly different thematic focus. The authors in this group share a view on the role of learning analysis and the development of self-regulation skills in the PBL context. They all highlight the importance of independent and interactive learning in PBL environments, emphasising the fundamental role of peer interactions and the use of poorly structured problems to improve cognitive and problem-solving skills.

The red cluster highlights the authors Dewi et al. and Harjono et al. This group has fewer connections and a smaller number of nodes, suggesting less centrality in relation to the network as a whole. However, the proximity of the nodes indicates that there is a strong relationship between the authors in this group, possibly focused on a specific subarea of research. The studies conducted by Dewi et al. and Harjono et al. focused on the PBL model for developing critical skills in students, particularly in science and mathematics teaching contexts, thus contributing to students' ability to solve complex problems and improve academic performance, with an emphasis on skills such as critical thinking and understanding abstract concepts.

The purple cluster features prominent authors such as Umar et al. and Olmedo-Torre et al. These authors focus on adapting PBL in response to the demands of online learning. Both studies examine the impacts of the shift to digital platforms on student engagement, collaboration, and emotional well-being, especially in technical areas.

3.3. Analysis of selected articles

After analysing eligibility to obtain accurate information on the topic of interest, 22 articles were selected (Table 1).

The proposals of the selected studies converged on the objective of improving teaching and knowledge in higher education courses. To this end, the use of problem-based learning and project-based learning methodologies was observed. Two studies also compared these two approaches (Table 1). Only the study conducted by Moreno-Palma et al. (2024) found no significant differences in learning with the application of PBL, this result could be summarized by the low number of participants and the type of assessment used, based on the Likert scale.

Sukackè et al. (2022) stated that evidence-based active learning in higher education is becoming a prerequisite for preparing future professionals not only for their professional lives but also for dealing with global issues. Teachers in higher education institutions are expected and encouraged to provide their students with active learning experiences, such as problem-based learning, projects and, more recently, challenges. According to the authors, teachers need to move away from a more traditional teacher-centred education to become instructional designers

of student-centred education.

Table 1: Characteristics of selected articles

Authors	Objective of the study	Methodology (n)	Results achieved	Strengths of the study	Limitations of the study
Sattarova et al., 2023	Analyse the effects of implementing problem-based learning (PBL).	Comparison between experimental group and control group. The final grades of the students in the subject were compared. (737)	Students who participated in PBL activities achieved higher grades than the control group.	Good sample size, comprising control and experimental groups.	The study did not use homogeneous groups, either in terms of gender or initial knowledge level. The study did not assess initial knowledge. The study did not assess cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects.
Rahim et al., 2024	Evaluate the effectiveness of merging project-based learning (PjBL) with STEAM education in metal welding curricula for students.	Pre- and post-tests compared the performance of an experimental pjbl-STEAM group to a traditionally taught control group. (64)	The PjBL-STEAM approach significantly outperformed traditional methods, as evidenced by higher average gain scores in the cognitive (0.763), affective (0.772), and psychomotor (0.759) domains.	The study conducted an assessment of prior knowledge. Good sample size. It assessed cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects. It used a control and experimental groups.	The study did not concern itself with the homogeneity of the groups.
Orhan, 2024	Investigate and compare the effectiveness of online and face-to-face learning on critical thinking skills, reading dispositions, reading comprehension abilities, and attitudes of students learning English as a foreign language.	Pre- and post-testing (English Attitude Scale, Sосу Critical Thinking Disposition Scale; Reading comprehension test; Critical Thinking Test) - Online PBL (23 - 13 women and 10 men) - Face-to-face PBL (23 - 14 women and 9 men) - Control group. (22 - 12 women and 10 men).	Whether online or in person, PBL significantly improved reading comprehension skills and attitudes, as well as critical thinking skills and dispositions.	The study conducted an assessment of prior knowledge. Good sample size. Used control and experimental groups. Homogeneity of groups in terms of gender.	The study did not assess cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects. It did not take prior knowledge into account when separating the groups.
Muerza et al., 2024	Analyse the application of PBL supplemented by videos created by students in the statistical teaching of Probability Calculus and Inferential Statistics in Business Administration and Management	Questionnaire, comparison between control and experimental groups. (82 students - 43.9% men and 56.1% women)	PBL significantly improves students' understanding and motivation, communication with teachers, teamwork skills, and grades.	Gender was taken into account when dividing the groups. Good sample size. Control and experimental groups. Skills were assessed.	The study did not assess students' prior knowledge.

Studies.						
Moreno-Palma et al., 2024	Develop computational thinking in the field of mathematics education among higher education students.	Pre- and post-testing of: - control (three males and 15 females) - experimental groups using a Likert scale (two males and 11 females)	The application of PBL did not influence learning.	The study conducted an assessment of prior knowledge. Good sample size. It used a control and experimental group.		There was no homogeneity among the groups in terms of gender. Cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects were not evaluated. The use of the Likert scale can be subjective.
Lopez-Gazpio, 2023	Present a methodology to improve Android programming teaching, focusing on addressing nutritional challenges.	Experimental group with PBL application (51). It was included another conventional group (27) and it was evaluated the average grade, using a questionnaire.	The group that had contact with PBL obtained higher average grades compared to conventional teaching.	Good sample size. It used control and experimental groups.		The study did not assess prior knowledge. Groups were not homogeneous. It did not assess cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects.
Liu et al., 2020	Evaluate the efficiency of PBL-CBL methodology in dentistry.	the Questionnaire and mean test - control (24 males and 22 females) - experimental (25 males and 21 females)	The experimental group had a higher degree of satisfaction. However, the experimental group considered that the methodology 'reduces the extracurricular workload'.	Good sample size. It used control and experimental groups. The study concerned about the homogeneity of groups in relation to gender.		The study did not assess students' prior knowledge. It did not assess cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects.
Jalinus & Putra, 2024	Enhance the student proficiency and 21st-century skills in vocational education through mobile programming applications.	Observation, questionnaires and tests. Control group in experimental group before and after testing. (30)	The study noted significant improvement in learning quality through the incorporation of PBL.	The study assessed prior knowledge. Control and experimental groups.		Relatively low number of participants, without observing the homogeneity of the groups. It did not evaluate cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects.
Batubara et al., 2023.	Develop and validate a methodology enriched with mobile technology for learning in the learning media course.	Application of the PjBL model assisted by mobile devices. Conducting individual tests (three), small group tests (12), and large group tests (120). Pre- and post-testing, N-gain.	The efficiency test showed a high average gain of 0.83 in the individual test, 0.74 in the small group test, and 0.73 in the large group test.	The study assessed prior knowledge. It assessed group size.		The study did not concern itself with group homogeneity. The individual group had a low number of participants. It did not assess cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects.
Baena-	Analyse the impact	Pre- and post-	The PBL	The study		The study did not

Luna et al., 2024	of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) methodology on the Intrapreneurial Intentions (II) of university students	testing using the Likert scale. (267 - 49.4% men and 50.6% women)	methodology significantly improved behaviour variables associated with potentially intrapreneurial behaviours. However, the values were lower for women than for men.	assessed prior knowledge. Homogeneity of groups in relation to gender.	assess cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects.
Bukumiric et al., 2022	Assess the effectiveness of PBL modules implemented in blended learning courses in medical student knowledge and satisfaction outcomes.	- Group with access to PBL modules - Group without access to PBL modules - blended learning course only (53)	Students in the HPBL group scored higher on problem solving. Problem solving was associated with being in the HPBL group and having a higher grade point average. All students in the HPBL group found the PBL modules useful for learning medical statistics.	Control and experimental groups.	The study did not assess prior knowledge. It did not assess cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects.
Wahyudi, 2020	Evaluate the application of the PBL methodology.	The Evaluation of the control and experimental groups. It did not report the groups that were homogeneous in terms of gender and age.	The experimental group showed better average learning outcomes.	The study evaluated control and experimental groups.	The study did not assess initial knowledge. Non-homogeneous groups. It did not present the number of individuals per group. This study did not assess cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects.
Farid et al., 2021	Implement PjBL in a hydraulic robotic arm project based on a PBL approach implemented through conventional numerical problems.	The study assessed which methodology was the best, based on the project or the problem, by evaluating and comparing the marks. (101)	PjBL proved to be more effective for undergraduate engineering education.	The study evaluated groups with PjBL and PBL. It assessed differences in knowledge between genders.	The study did not assess initial knowledge. It did not use a control group. It did not assess cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects.
Kan & Saka, 2021	Compare PjBL and PBL.	Evaluate PjBL and PBL. The average grades for the physics course and the placement test results were used. (20 men and 28 women, in groups of 10 and 14).	PjBL is more effective than PBL. Both methodologies contribute to the teaching of physics.	The study evaluated groups with PjBL and PBL. It assessed differences in knowledge between genders.	The study did not assess initial knowledge. It did not use a control group. It did not assess cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects. Small number of participants per group.

Liu & Mu, 2022	Test ideas for effective education in computer and network plans.	N-GAIN pre-test and post-test questionnaire. 92 in the control group and 92 in the experimental group.	The use of PBL improved collaborative inquiry. Pre- and post-test data could reveal a 20% increase in network learning ideas.	The study evaluated control and experimental groups. It assessed initial knowledge. Good sample size.	The study did not assess cognitive, and affective, and psychomotor aspects. There was no homogeneity among the groups in terms of knowledge and gender.
Chang et al., 2022	Design a teaching process based on the concept of flipped classrooms. With learning objectives, learning content, and group activities.	Pre-test and post-test, questionnaires, Likert scale and evaluation. - Control group: 49 - Experimental group: 47 students, who were divided into heterogeneous subgroups according to their marks in the mid-term programming exam.	- The experimental group showed improvements in learning compared to the control group; - The experimental group showed no difference in learning among students with high scores before and after the strategy; - Students with average scores showed improvements in learning outcomes, before and after the strategy; - Significant differences in learning among students with low scores before and after the strategy.	The study assessed initial knowledge. Control and experimental groups. It separated the groups according to knowledge. It used Likert scale and assessment. Good sample size.	The study did not separate the groups according to gender. It did not assess cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects.
Situmorang, 2022	Implement learning-based approaches in order to develop it.	Pre-test and post-test. Questionnaires, Likert scale 1-4 and multiple-choice test. (73)	Pre-test 23.63±4.08 post-test 87.18±6.33. The PjBL model is effective in guiding students to study independently, increase knowledge and skills.	The study assessed initial knowledge. It used questionnaire, Likert scale as a supplement.	There was no control group. Cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects were not evaluated. Groups were not homogeneous in terms of gender and knowledge.
Pal'ová & Vejcka, 2022	Evaluate the students' critical thinking skills and competencies in analytical chemistry.	Gain test. Control and experimental groups. (552)	Pre-test 56.35% ± 11.72% post-test 71.60% ± 11.76%. PjBL, the efficiency of the educational process increased as the average learning gain of the class scored an average of 4.62 points more in total.	The study assessed initial knowledge. Control and experimental groups. Good sample size.	The study did not use homogeneous groups in terms of gender and knowledge. It did not assess cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects.
Mursid et al., 2022	Assess the effectiveness of PjBL in education.	Pre- and post-testing. (80 students, including both men and	Experimental group I – blended PjBL model achieved the best learning outcomes in	The study assessed initial knowledge. Control and experimental	The study did not use homogeneous groups in terms of gender and knowledge. It did not assess cognitive,

	women)	engineering design.	groups.	affective, and psychomotor aspects.	
Maros et al., 2023	Examine the effect of the combined project-based learning (PjBL) model.	60 students in the control group and 63 students in the experimental group.	The use of PBL improved learning, but was considered complicated by some students.	The study evaluated control and experimental groups. Good sample size.	The study did not assess initial knowledge. It did not use homogeneous groups. It did not assess cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects.
Hurtado et al., 2023	Encourage the use of PBL.	Gain test, pre- and post-test. (19 students from UNICAMP. 26 students from PUJ).	Students achieved higher grades after PBL instruction at both institutions.	The study assessed initial knowledge. It assessed two different contexts.	The groups were not homogeneous in terms of gender, initial knowledge, and environment. It did not assess cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects. It did not assess initial knowledge.
Rodriguez-Sanchez et al., 2024	Evaluate the use of PBL in two higher education institutions.	Evaluation of the control and experimental groups. (2017–2018 = 9 and 2018–2023 = 28)	The integration of PBL led to higher grades and increased motivation.	Evaluation of the control and experimental groups. The year used as a control has a low number of participants.	The study did not assess initial knowledge. The control group did not have the same conditions as the other groups. It did not assess influencing factors such as gender.

With regard to the evaluation methods used to verify the efficiency of PBL, most of them (54.54%) used the gain test, which is carried out through pre- and post-testing. Among these articles, six of them worked with a control group by using a traditional teaching model, and also an experimental group using the PBL methodology (Chang et al., 2022; Pal'ová & Vejacka, 2022; Jalinus & Putra, 2024; Moreno-Palma et al., 2024; Orhan, 2024; Rahim et al., 2024). Six articles worked only with an experimental group, evaluating the situation before and after the application of the methodology (Liu & Mu, 2022; Situmorang, 2022; Mursid et al., 2022; Batubara et al., 2023; Baena-Luna et al., 2024; Hurtado et al., 2023) (Table 1).

In the case of using control and experimental groups, Jalinus and Putra (2024) pointed out that comparing these two groups, when evaluating teaching efficiency, may be unable to effectively regulate the external circumstances that impact the execution of this type of research, due to various individual factors that affect each student.

Interviews and questionnaires were also used in some studies as a complementary assessment tool (Liu et al., 2020; Liu & Mu, 2022; Chang et al., 2022; Situmorang, 2022; Lopez-Gazpio, 2023; Jalinus & Putra, 2024; Muerza et al., 2024) (Table 2). According to Liu and Mu

(2022), these methods can be used for the analytical approach to qualitative data and seek to identify different characteristics of the study. According to the authors who used this tool, it contributes to the collection of information such as student acceptance of the methodology, identification of challenges and benefits of applying PBL, the efficiency of the approach, the level of engagement and satisfaction, the development of practical skills, the student-teacher relationship, necessary interventions, evaluation of cognitive aspects, affective aspects, among others.

In addition to those characteristics mentioned above, the authors also used assessments, Likert scales, and multiple-choice tests. Likert scales generally receive scores ranging from 1 to 4 or 5, and these values are added together to calculate the participant's average score.

The study by Moreno-Palma et al. (2024) used a five-point Likert scale in the pre- and post-tests, consisting of 29 items that were grouped into five factors as follows: creativity (8 items), algorithmic thinking (6 items), cooperativeness (4 items), critical thinking (5 items), and problem solving (6 items). However, these authors did not observe any effect of the application of PBL in this group using the Likert scale for assessment and did not recommend its use in future studies.

A questionnaire template was applied by Liu et al. (2020), in which the authors used nine questions, which participants could answer with “yes” or “no”, to assess their level of satisfaction with the application of the PBL methodology and the traditional teacher-centred methodology. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the questionnaires and Likert scale are not standard and will depend on the area of study and the analysis the authors aim to perform.

The other articles report that the assessment was carried out using the average marks obtained by the groups, i.e., there was no prior assessment of knowledge.

In all studies, except that of Moreno-Palma et al. (2024), it was observed that the PBL methodology promoted improvements in student learning. The degree of this increase varied among authors and the different methodologies applied, reaching an increase of up to 46.2%, as reported by Pal'ová and Vejcka (2022). However, Chang et al. (2022) found that the level of learning depends on the scores obtained in the pre-test, with lower scores tending to result in more significant learning gains for students. The authors suggest that this effect may be related to heterogeneous grouping, in which students with high and average scores guided and discussed content with those who scored low.

The two studies that compared problem-based learning and project-based learning methodologies (Farid et al., 2021; Kan & Saka, 2021) indicated that project-based learning is more effective than problem-based learning. According to Miranda et al. (2020), one of the main characteristics that distinguishes project-based learning from other methodologies is the creation

of a final product. In addition, project-based learning focuses on the mobilisation of knowledge and presents activities that are generally closer to real professional practices, especially in engineering courses.

According to Situmorang (2022), the problem-based learning approach is effective in guiding students to study independently, expanding their knowledge and skills. The implementation of problem-based learning contributes to the development of critical thinking skills, including the ability to organise one's own projects, execute project stages such as data collection, analysis and interpretation, and report on the findings obtained. However, Mursid al. (2022) emphasised that teachers should combine a problem-based learning model with traditional methods to ensure better results, in addition to fostering creative thinking skills, thereby increasing the efficiency of the methodology.

In addition to learning, some studies have shown that the PBL methodology also improves other educational aspects, such as communication between teachers and students. Students become more proactive in seeking solutions to problems, improving the expression of doubts and opinions, increasing motivation to learn, and improving cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects (Bukumiric et al., 2022; Jalinus & Putra, 2024; Muerza et al., 2024; Orhan, 2024; Rahim et al., 2024; Rodriguez-Sanchez et al., 2024).

Sukackè et al. (2022) highlighted that there are criticisms of the implementation of the PBL methodology. These include a lack of understanding of the processes involved in active learning and student development, such as the improvement of teamwork skills, the complexity of social interactions and their impact on learning, as well as limitations in the measures used to assess the effectiveness of active learning on student performance and learning outcomes.

One factor pointed out by Liu et al. (2020) is the time required to apply the PBL methodology, which can impact the curriculum workload and interfere with the development of other subjects. For this reason, it is advisable to consider adjustments to the curriculum and workload distribution before the start of the course, ensuring that the implementation of PBL is properly planned.

Sattarova et al. (2023) pointed out that one of the difficulties in implementing the PBL methodology is related to the country's educational culture, which can hinder its application, especially in undergraduate education. In this context, both administrators and teachers often show little interest in replacing traditional teaching methods. On the other hand, research indicates that the application of PBL has shown positive results in education, thus highlighting the evidence that the adoption of this pedagogical approach in the future may be beneficial.

Among the assessment methods used in studies to verify the effectiveness of PBL, the gain test was the most widely used for quantitative assessment and proved to be the most suitable

for this purpose. This test allows for the assessment of students' prior knowledge, which is essential for subsequently determining the effectiveness of the methodology. In addition, one of the studies showed that students with low pre-test averages tend to show significant increases in their learning after the application of PBL. Thus, the initial assessment of knowledge should be considered in research that seeks to measure the efficiency of the methodology.

In this study, it was observed that some studies did not pay sufficient attention to experimental homogeneity, and it would be ideal for the groups to be more uniform. One of the aspects neglected in the composition of the groups was the distribution by gender, since Mourato (2021) highlighted differences in the perception and learning of men and women in activities that use the PBL methodology.

Thus, it is evident that gender should be considered in the assessment of learning. Besides, a prior assessment of students is necessary to identify their initial level of knowledge, making the pre-test an appropriate tool for studies of this type. As noted by Chang et al. (2022), groups with more advanced knowledge tend to be less influenced by the application of PBL, while students with low pre-test scores show significant gains in the post-test.

3.4. Integrative Model and Evidence Validation

Based on the findings of the systematic literature review, we propose the development of an integrative model to evaluate the efficiency of applying the PBL methodology in learning. The use of pre- and post-test assessments is recommended, associated with criteria such as: comparison of averages, presence of a control group (without participation in PBL activities) and an experimental group, in addition to the formation of homogeneous groups, considering the degree of prior knowledge and gender of the participants. This model is represented in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Integrative model developed based on the evidence analysed

Figure 6 presents the criteria to be considered for the development of an Evaluation Model for the PBL methodology in Higher Education, based on the analysis of the systematic review of the literature. Thus, the results obtained may reflect the application of PBL with greater reliability. It should be noted that, when correctly implemented, the PBL methodology can offer several benefits compared to traditional methodologies, including improvements in learning, communication, socialisation, autonomy, and the development of cognitive, affective, and psychomotor skills.

4. Final Considerations

The assessment methods used in the studies to verify the effectiveness of PBL were pre- and post-tests (gain tests), interviews, questionnaires, Likert scales, and multiple-choice tests. Of these, gain tests were most commonly used for quantitative assessment and appear to be the most suitable for this purpose. The other tests, mainly for qualitative assessments, were used more to verify issues related to the participants' skills and abilities.

The lack of homogeneity of the groups tested, observed in some studies, may interfere with the results achieved, as there were no criteria for selecting the groups, either in relation to the students' level of learning or gender, given that these factors can generate unreliable results. Thus, the ideal research would be to conduct a careful assessment initially to define the most homogeneous groups tested.

It was also observed that group work can generate better results. In this sense, it should be noted that students with lower learning rates can develop their skills and abilities, given that other students who learn more easily can pass on instructions to those with greater learning difficulties.

For future research, there is a need to define more precisely the methodology for applying PBL, considering both the participating students and the environment and professionals responsible for implementing it. It should be noted that the methodology is still rarely applied in higher education, and it is essential to improve the training of the professionals who conduct it.

References

- BAENA-LUNA, P.; SÁNCHEZ-TORNÉ, I.; GARCÍA-RÍO, E.; PÉREZ-SUÁREZ, M. Influence of the problem-based learning methodology on the intrapreneurial intentions of university students. *The International Journal of Management Education*, v. 22, n. 3, 101024, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2024.101024>.
- BATUBARA, H. H.; NOOR, H.; SIREGAR, P.; IHWANAH, A.; HUSNI, M.; WIBOWO, D. R.; ARIANI, D. N. Developing a mobile-assisted Project-Based Learning model for a learning media course. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, v. 17, n. 17, p. 1-4, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v17i17.42621>.
- BAYRAM, H.; DEVECI, H. The Effect of Problem-Based Learning on Students' entrepreneurship level insocial studies course. *International Journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, v. 9, n. 2, p. 359-377, 2022.
- BUKUMIRIC, Z.; ILIC, A.; PAJICIN, M.; SREBRO, D.; MILICEVIC, S.; SPAIC, D.; et al. Effects of problem-based learning modules within blended learning courses in medical statistics – A randomized controlled pilot study. *PLoS ONE*, v. 17, n. 1, e0263015, 2022.
- CHANG, Y. H.; YAN, Y. C.; LU, Y. T. Effects of combining different collaborative learning strategies with problem-based learning in a flipped classroom on program language learning. *Sustainability*, v. 14, n. 9, 5282, 2022.
- FARID, T.; ALI, S.; SAJID, M.; AKHTAR, K. Sustainability of project-based learning by incorporating transdisciplinary design in fabrication of hydraulic robot arm. *Sustainability*, v. 13, n. 14, 7949, 2021.
- FERRAZ FILHO, B. F.; DOS SANTOS, A. C.; DA SILVA, R. O.; BITTENCOURT, W.; PEIXOTO, R. N.; MARCELINO, R. Aprendizagem Baseada em Problema (pbl): uma inovação educacional?. *Revista Cesumar–Ciências Humanas e Sociais Aplicadas*, v. 22, n. 2, p. 403-424, 2017.
- HURTADO, J. A.; USECHE, A. C.; MASIERO, B. S. Project-Based Learning: Authentic engineering assessment supported by model design. *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy*, v. 13, n. 6, p. 1-7, 2023.
- JALINUS, N.; PUTRA, R. R. Implementation of Project-Based Learning computational thinking models in mobile programming courses. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, v. 18, n. 11, p. 1-7, 2024.
- KAN, S.; ZEKI SAKA, A. The comparison of problem based and project based learning methods in physics teaching. *Croatian Journal of Education*, v. 23, n. 3, p. 731-765, 2021.
- KASUGA, W.; MARO, W.; PANGANI, I. Effect of Problem-Based Learning on developing science process skills and learning achievement on the topic of safety in our environment. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, v. 19, n. 3, p. 872–886, 2022.
- LAWLESS, K. A.; BROWN, S. W.; RHOADS, C.; LYNN, L.; NEWTON, S. D.; BRODOWIKSA, K.; et al. Promoting students' science literacy skills through a simulation of

international negotiations: The GlobalEd 2 Project. *Computers in Human Behavior*, v. 78, p. 389–396, 2018.

LIU, M.; MU, X. Analysis of computer network technology on new media problem-based learning (PBL) teaching method. *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, p. 1-10, 2022.

LIU, Y.; XU, Y.; LI, Y.; WU, Q. Application of problem-based learning and case-based learning integrated method in the teaching of maxillary sinus floor augmentation in implant dentistry. *PeerJ*, v. 8, e8353, 2020.

LOPEZ-GAZPIO, I. Bridging theory and practice: an innovative approach to android programming education through nutritional application development and Problem-Based Learning. *Applied Sciences*, v. 13, n. 22, 12140, 2023.

MARIANO, A. M.; ROCHA, M. S. Revisão da literatura: apresentação de uma abordagem integradora. *AEDEM International Conference*, p. 427-442, 2017. Disponível em: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ari-Mariano/publication/319547360_Revisao_da_Literatura_Apresentacao_de_uma_Abordagem_Integradora/links/59beb024aca272aff2dee36f/Revisao-da-Literatura-Apresentacao-de-uma-Abordagem-Integradora.pdf. Acesso em: 13 abr 2025.

MAROS, M.; KORENKOVA, M.; FILA, M.; LEVICKY, M.; SCHOBEROVA, M. Project-based learning and its effectiveness: evidence from Slovakia. *Interactive Learning Environments*, v. 31, n. 7, p. 4147-4155, 2023.

MIRANDA, M.; SAIZ-LINARES, A.; DA COSTA, A.; CASTRO, J. Active, experiential and reflective training in civil engineering: Evaluation of a project-based learning proposal. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, v. 45, p. 937–956, 2020.

MOHER, D.; LIBERATI, A.; TETZLAFF, J.; ALTMAN, D. G. The PRISMA Group. Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses: The PRISMA Statement. *PLoS Medicine*, v. 21, n. 7, e1000097, 2009.

MORENO-PALMA, N.; HINOJO-LUCENA, F. J.; ROMERO-RODRÍGUEZ, J. M.; CÁCERES-RECHE, M. P. Effectiveness of problem-based learning in the unplugged computational thinking of university students. *Education Sciences*, v. 14, n. 7, 693, 2024.

MOURATO, D. Aprendizagem por problemas, identidade de gênero e learnability em projetos finais nas licenciaturas. *Revista Ibérica de Sistemas y Tecnologías de Informacion*, v. 45, n. 10, p. 674-688, 2021.

MUERZA, V.; GARGALLO, P.; SALVADOR, M.; TURÓN, A. Impact of Problem-Based Learning on the perception, understanding, and application of statistical concepts in business administration and management students. *Sustainability*, v. 16, n. 4, 1591, 2024.

MURSID, R.; SARAGIH, A. H.; HARTONO, R. The effect of the blended project-based learning model and creative thinking ability on engineering students' learning outcomes. *International Journal of Education in Mathematics, Science and Technology*, v. 10, n. 1, p. 218-235, 2022.

ORHAN, A. Online or in-class problem based learning: Which one is more effective in enhancing learning outcomes and critical thinking in higher education EFL classroom?. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, v. 40, n. 5, p. 2351-2368, 2024.

PAĀOVÁ, D.; VEJÁČKA, M. Project-based Learning in the University Course and its Effectiveness. *TEM Journal*, v. 11, n. 4, p. 1477-1484, 2022.

RAHIM, B.; AMBIYAR, A.; WASKITO, W.; FORTUNA, A.; PRASETYA, F.; ANDRIANI, C.; SALMAN, A. Effectiveness of Project-Based Learning in metal welding technology course with steam approach in vocational education. *TEM Journal*, v. 2, p. 1481-1492, 2024.

RAHMAN, A.; ILWANDRI, I.; SANTOSA, T. A.; GUNAWAN, R. G.; SUHARYAT, Y.; PUTRA, R.; SOFIANORA, A. Eficiência do modelo de aprendizagem baseada em problemas na aprendizagem de ciências: um estudo de meta-análise. *Jurnal Olahraga*, v. 8, n. 2, p. 713-726, 2023.

RODRIGUEZ-SANCHEZ, C.; ORELLANA, R.; FERNANDEZ BARBOSA, P. R.; BORROMEO, S.; VAQUERO, J. Insights 4.0: Transformative learning in industrial engineering through problem-based learning and project-based learning. *Computer Applications in Engineering Education*, v. 32, n. 4, e22736, 2024.

SATTAROVA, U.; ARSENIJEVIC, J.; GROOT, W. An analysis of Problem-Based Learning vs. traditional teaching among students in Azerbaijan. *Education Sciences*, v. 13, n. 12, 1167, 2023.

SITUMORANG, M.; SINAGA, M.; SITORUS, M.; SUDRAJAT, A. Implementation of project-based learning innovation to develop students' critical thinking skills as a strategy to achieve analytical chemistry competencies. *Chemistry*, v. 56, n. 1, S41-S51, 2022.

SONG, H.-D.; GRABOWSKI, B. L.; KOSZALKA, T. A.; HARKNESS, W. L. Patterns of instructional design factors prompting reflective thinking in middle-school and college level problem based learning environments. *Instructional Science*, v. 34, n. 1, p. 63–87, 2006.

SUKACKÉ, V.; GUERRA, A. O. P. D. C.; ELLINGER, D.; CARLOS, V.; PETRONIENÉ, S.; GAIZIŪNIENĒ, L.; BROSE, A. Towards active evidence-based learning in engineering education: A systematic literature review of PBL, PjBL, and CBL. *Sustainability*, v. 14, n. 21, 13955, 2022.

WAHYUDI, W. The effectiveness of sharing blended project based learning (SBPBL) model implementation in operating system course. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, v. 15, n. 5, p. 202-211, 2020.

WOHLIN, C. Guidelines for Snowballing in Systematic Literature Studies and a Replication in Software Engineering. *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering*, Karlskrona, p. 1–10, 2014.

ZULYUSRI, ELFIRA, I.; VIOLITA, A.; SANTOSA, T. A. Meta-Analysis Study: Correlation study of the influence of motivation on student learning outcomes. *International Journal of Education and Literature*, v. 1, n. 3, p. 34–45, 2022.